

Step-wise Instruction on Predictive Run of Neff RF & Pconf RF

The Neff_RF and Pconf_RF was developed in the *Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis (Weka)* Version 3.8.3 environment, an open-source machine learning execution software package developed at the University of Waikato, New Zealand. The software package can be freely downloaded from <http://old-www.cms.waikato.ac.nz/~ml/weka/>. This document aims to provide a stepwise procedure for executing the *Neff_RF and Pconf_RF* for making predictive runs with new datasets as follows:

Step-1:

After successful installation of the package, the application needs to be opened and the following window will be on the computer screen:

Step-2:

The 'Explorer' button on the above screen needs to be clicked to open the 'Weka Explorer' window as shown in the following screenshot:

Step-3:

In 'Weka Explorer' window press 'Preprocess' button and then press 'Open file...' to open a window called 'Open', where the template for the input (*Input_Prediction_Template.CSV*) can be browsed and uploaded to the system. Before this, the user has to save the predictors in the template in the required format and units. Don't make any format change to *Input_Prediction_Template.CSV*.

Step-4:

After loading the input to the 'Weka Explorer' the other options for processing the data will be activated. The user needs to press 'Classify' button to continue the analysis relevant to this exercise.

Step-5:

Once the 'Classify' button is pressed, the following window will be opened:

This is the window where all our analyses will be carried out. First of all the user needs to upload the model configuration to the software. For doing that user needs to right-click on the space under 'Result list' and select 'load model'.

When the user will right-click on the space under 'Result list', the 'Open' window will pop-up and will give the options to browse the directory where the "Neff_RF.model" and "Pconf_RF.model" file is saved. Then the model configuration needs to be selected and opened. After successfully loading the model RF-HID-S.model to 'Result list', the model trees and the eight pertinent predictors can be visualized in the 'Classifier output' window.

Step-6:

In the next step, the user needs to supply test data (Input_Prediction_Template.CSV) on which the predictive run has to be executed. For example, only five instances are provided in Input_Prediction_Template.CSV. User has to just copy and paste their input data in respective columns and may use this template for the number of instances according to their convenience.

The user needs to select the 'Supplied test set' option in the 'Test option' window and click on 'Set...'. Subsequently, the 'Test instances' window will pop-up, where the user needs to click on 'Open file...' to browse the directory that contains *Input_Prediction_Template.CSV*. It can be very well marked here that without selecting the test dataset the 'Relation', 'Instances', and 'Attributes' will be with 'None' values. Once the user clicks on 'Open file...' the "Open" window will pop-up and the input can be selected and opened.

Once the *Input_Prediction_Template.CSV* is opened, the 'Relation', 'Instances', and 'Attributes' will show their respective values in the 'Test instances' window. That confirms that the inputs are uploaded successfully to the modeling environment for this particular run. So, the user needs to close the 'Test instances' window.

Step-7:

In this step, the user needs to make the adjustment to the 'Classifier evaluation options', which can be opened by clicking on 'More option' under the 'Test option' window. Here the user needs to set the 'Output predictions' to *.CSV* as shown in the next screenshot and close the 'Classifier evaluation options'

Step-8:

Here the user needs to right-click on the *.model* files in 'Result list' and click on 'Re-apply this model's configuration'. Once the 'Re-apply this model's configuration' option is clicked the model will be ready to be used to make the predictive run. Then the user needs to right-click on the ".model" loaded in 'Result list' and click on 'Re-evaluate model on current test set'.

Once the 'Re-evaluate model on current test set' is clicked a pop-up called 'ClassifierPanel' will be opened and will ask for wrapping the classifier in an "InputMappedClassifier" because the class variable in the *Input_Prediction_Template.CSV* is kept blank and it is not a numeric value, which will be predicted using the predictors in *Input_Prediction_Template.CSV*. So, the user needs to press 'Yes' and soon after that, the model will generate the predictions. The run time for each predictive run will depend on the number of instances under consideration. The status of the predictive run can be checked in 'Log' window at the bottom of 'Weka explorer' window.

Once the predictions will be generated the user has two options for saving the results:

1. By right-clicking on ".model" (the "Neff_RF.model" and "Pconf_RF.model") loaded in 'Result list' and selecting 'Save result buffer', which will provide options to save the result buffer in the targeted directory and that can be opened using excel for further processing.
2. By right-clicking on "Neff_RF.model" and "Pconf_RF.model" in 'Result list' and selecting 'Visualize classifier errors', which will open 'Weka Classifier Visualize'. In 'Weka Classifier Visualize' user needs to press the save button to save the result in *.arff* format, which can be easily converted to excel format for further processing.